

ULTRAWAVE

Horizon 2020 ULTRAWAVE

Ultra-capacity wireless layer beyond 100 GHz based on millimetre wave Traveling Wave Tubes

WP5 Deliverable D5.2: Photonic Transmitter

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Dissemination level

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PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including Commission Services)	
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D5.2 describes the design and the fabrication of the G-band photonic transmitter developed for the ULTRAWAVE project. This deliverable is associated with task 5.5 (Photonic transmitter design and test).

The photonic transmitter is based on the heterodyne beat between two spectral lines in a unitravelling photodiode to reach the G-band carrier frequency and the external modulation due to its high stability and reliability. The impact of critical parameters on the performance of the transmitter will be analysed, especially in terms of capacity and linearity.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

IDU: In-door unit (multiplex)
DFB: distributed feedback laser
MZM: Mach Zehnder Modulator
ODU: Out-door unit
OPLL: optical phase lock loop
PLL: Phase-Locked Loop or Phase Lock Loop
PM: Phase Modulator
PtP: Point to point.
PmP: Point to multipoint
QPSK: Quadrature Phase-Shift Keying
UTC: Uni Travelling Carrier photodiode
WSS: Wavelength selective switch

1 PHOTONIC TRANSMITTER ARCHITECTURE

Based upon system description and preliminary specifications of the G-band fronthaul in deliverables D2.1 and D2.2, this deliverable provides the design and the fabrication of the photonic transmitter for the G-band. The general concept for ULTRAWAVE is shown in Figure 1. The aim of the photonic transmitter is providing a set of 2.5 Gbps channels to be radiated in the G-band to feed a PmP hub through wireless PtP links.

Figure 1.- ULTRAWAVE general concept

1.1 Sub-millimeter wireless photonic generation

Different techniques exist for the photonic heterodyne generation of wireless signals. They mainly differ from the method used to generate the optical carriers. They can be classified as [1], [2]:

- Free running: A technique based on the use of two independent optical sources spaced the wireless signal central frequency. Although simple, this approach offers little stability in the central frequency of the photonic generated wireless signal and poor phase noise due to the lack of coherence between sources.
- Optical injection locking: Coherence between optical signals can be achieved through injection locking. In this approach, a master laser is modulated to generate sidebands which are injected into two slave lasers which are locked to the master sidebands. Thus, the output of the two slave lasers are phase correlated and therefore after photodetection a beat note with low phase noise is generated.
- Optical phase lock loop: It relies on having two independent optical sources and actively locking the phase of one of them to that of the second through an optical analogue of a PLL (phase lock loop) by comparing the phase of the beat note with that of an RF reference from a microwave generator laser by an OPPL.
- External modulation: Another approach is based on exploiting the nonlinearity of external modulators to generate high quality millimetre-wave signals. Higher harmonics can be reached following this approach [3]. Additionally, it allows the capacity to broadly tune the central frequency of the generated millimetre-wave signal and eases the generation of the optical multiplex to populate the whole wireless band with a single system.

Operation in the G-band imposes a considerable challenge for all of these approaches. To reach this band with seed local oscillators of low frequency, high multiplication factors are needed and therefore external modulation is in principle the most suitable technique.

1.2 G-band transmitter general architecture

Due to their better stability, tunability, simplicity and capability to reach the G-band, external modulation was selected for ULTRAWAVE as the preferred technique for the implementation of the photonic transmitter.

The general block diagram of the architecture concept is shown in Figure 2 where external modulation with two cascaded phase modulators (PM) is used to generate the optical multiplex. In particular, a set of optical carriers is generated through external phase modulation fed by a microwave oscillator (e.g. at 24.59 GHz) of a single wavelength optical source (at 1550 nm). One optical carrier is kept unmodulated while some other carriers are modulated by a QPSK Giga-baud “data channel” through a DP MZM (I & Q Mach Zehnder Modulator). The modulated optical carriers are then multiplexed and combined with the unmodulated carrier whose frequency spacing is around 300 GHz. The ensemble is transported from the NIU to the ODU through an optical single-mode fiber. At the ODU, a UTC Photodiode (Uni Travelling Carrier) is used to beat the unmodulated optical carrier with the data channels to generate a signal in the G-band. The mix provides a multiplex of modulated data on G band sub-carriers.

Figure 2: Photonic transmitter concept.

1.3 G-band photonic transmitter design

The general G-band photonic transmitter concept based on external modulation (Figure 2) has been particularized in the design shown in Figure 3. The optical demultiplexing has been implemented using fiber Bragg gratings. Photonic implementations of sub-THz data communication transmitters generally employ WSS (wavelength selective switches). Although WSS are very versatile devices, the ones suitable for this kind of experiments are also bulky and rather expensive. Therefore, a slightly different approach has been followed in ULTRAWAVE, based on the use of fiber Bragg gratings to select the desired carriers, as shown in Figure 3. This approach offers better compactness and reduces cost over the WSS-based solution. The different branches of the demultiplexing stage have to be time matched to ensure good quality of the generated signals.

Figure 3: G-band photonic transmitter design.

The optical comb is generated through a two-stage external modulation of a DFB laser. Theoretical estimations [1] have shown that the laser output power should be >13 dBm, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: RF output power to RF input power.

In relation to the external modulation, phase modulation is employed due to its better performance in terms of harmonic generation efficiency, stability and simplicity due to the lack of biasing. Two low- V_{π} phase modulators (PM) have been employed. To reach the output frequency of 300 GHz, the $\pm 6^{\text{th}}$ harmonics need to be generated and sent to the photodetector. Therefore, the microwave oscillator should have a central frequency of 25 GHz. The need of tunable signals in the G-band is challenging. Following the approach proposed in Figure 3, tunability of the generated G-band signals can be controlled from this seed oscillator.

The need of two external modulators to reach enough combined modulation index requires phase matching of the two microwave feeding signals to have a coherent constructive addition. It can be implemented both in the optical and electrical domains. Both have been theoretically and experimentally evaluated in this project. Figure 5 shows the experimental difference in performance between both approaches. The harmonics generation is more efficient using electrical phase shifting

due to reduced insertion loss given by the quadratic response of the photonic link, in particular, the improvement in the strength of the harmonic power is around 5 dB.

Figure 5: Optical comb generated using electrical (blue) and optical (red) phase shift matching.

A theoretical study to define the required power of the microwave local oscillator driving the PMs has been performed. A theoretical model shows the dependence of the generated G-band signal on the local oscillator. Figure 6 shows the dependence of the 6th harmonic power as a function of the microwave LO due to the Bessel response of the combination of the two PMs [1]. Taking into account the saturation of the electrical amplifier, the target power for the microwave oscillator has been set at 25 dBm.

Figure 6: Power of the 6th harmonic vs RF power used at external modulation.

Given these design parameters, the theoretical estimation of the optical comb obtained from the block diagram shown in Figure 3 is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Theoretical estimation of the tunable optical comb.

Finally, photodetection is performed using a unitravelling carrier photodiode. In particular, a G-band UTC-PD from NEL (NTT Electronics Corp), shown in Figure 8, is used.

Figure 8: G-band UTC-PD from NEL (OD-PMJ-13001).

The interface with the electronic subsystems to be developed in the framework of ULTRAWAVE is going to be based on a 20-mm long WR-3 waveguide with flat waveguide flange.

Figure 9 shows a picture of the photonic transmitter at UPV labs.

Figure 9: Photonic transmitter.

2 CONCLUSIONS

Deliverable D5.2 has reported on the design and fabrication of the photonic transmitter for the G-band developed in the framework of Task 5.5 of EU project ULTRAWAVE. The performance are in line with the specifications.

3 REFERENCES

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